

An Overview of Fuzzy Based Mathematical Models on Covid-19 Outbreak

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Abstract: The present scenario of the world and public health is knocking hard with a big question of critical uncertainty of COVID-19 because of its imprecise database as per daily positive cases recorded all over the world and in India as well. In this review work we are interested in mathematical model for COVID-19 by using fuzzy logic-based system. Overall, this systematic review provides an appropriate platform for further research by identifying the research needs in the domain of COVID-19 outbreak.

Key Words: Fuzzy Logic-Based System (FRBS), COVID-19 Outbreak, Global Corona Pandemic, Fuzzy Logic, Fuzzy inference system (FIS), Corona Viruses.

INTRODUCTION

The novel coronavirus (COVID-19 or SARS-COV-2) epidemic has involved into a global pandemic. More than 17 million individuals have been infected globally, yielding to more than 45 Lakh death cases in the world till now. Rapid human-to-human transmission accompanied by unrevealed nature of the virus has led to a tremendous outbreak. The pandemic SARS-CoV-2 has become an undying virus to spread sustainable disease named COVID-19 for upcoming few years. Isolation from the infected individual or community is the recommended choice to save our existence. As the human is the only carrier so in that case if the host carriers are isolated from each other then it might be possible to control the spread or positive rates of infected population. Whereas only isolation might not be the only recommended solution.

The worldwide overwhelming number of COVID-19 infection created an emergency-like situation among the government agencies in pooling the resources and handling the epidemic at all levels. This has impacted greatly the growth and economy and the freedom in leading a happy life of all human beings. Predictions are always happening after the event has occurred. Several mathematical models and computerized simulations have cropped up as an aid in planning and designing the strategies to meet the unexpected demands of the health care system.

The ongoing COVID-19 outbreak poses a challenge for model designers, as there is limited data on pathway of virus, and epidemiological characteristics of new coronavirus are still not fully defined. The transmission of an emerging novel respiratory pathogen is accompanied by uncertainty concerning its key epidemiological, clinical and biological characteristics, particularly its ability to transmission in human population and its virulence (case severity). Medical experts take the diagnostic decision depending on familiarity, experience, knowledge, capability and perception of the medical scientist. On dealing with the global corona pandemic, it is not easy to follow a specific diagnostic way without any error. In the traditional approach, a physician is required to diagnose disease based on historical and clinical data but the Fuzzy Rule Based system will help physicians as well as individuals to detect intelligently disease at any location of the world.

What is Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is a multi-valued logic which was introduced by Zadeh in order to deal with vague and indecisive ideas. It has been described as an extension to the conventional Aristotelian and Boolean logic as it deals with “degrees of truth” rather than absolute values of “0 and 1” or “true/false”. Fuzzy logic is not like a computer software which understands only binary functions or concrete values like 1.5, 2.8 etc. instead, it is similar to human thinking and interpretation and gives meaning to expressions like “often”, “smaller” and “higher”. Fuzzy logic takes into account that real world is complex and there is uncertainty.

Characteristics of Fuzzy Logic

There are a few basic principles of fuzzy logic which were laid down by Zadeh in 1992.

- Exact reasoning is viewed as a limiting case of approximate reasoning.
- Everything is a matter of degree.
- Knowledge is interpreted as a collection of elastic, fuzzy constraints on a collection of variables.
- Inference is viewed as a process of propagation of elastic constraints.
- Any logical system can be “fuzzified”.

Fuzzy Sets

A classical set of binary logic has “crisp” boundaries whereas fuzzy sets have fuzzy or imprecise boundaries. A fuzzy set consists of linguistic variables where values are words and not numerical. A fuzzy set can be represented by the following equations-

Fuzzy Sets: low, medium and high

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ Where A is a fuzzy set in X and $\mu_A(x)$ is the membership function, which can have any value between 0 and 1 inclusive.

Fuzzy Rules

Fuzzy rule is based on “if then” rule and connects the different input and output fuzzy variables. It can be expressed as:

If x is A then y is B

Where A is the antecedent and B is the consequent. Fuzzy rules are similar to common sense rules as they resemble human thinking and are based on human experience. For example, in order to control intracranial pressure (ICP) in a patient with traumatic brain injury, sedation is often required but needs to be carefully monitored. A simple rule can be, “If the ICP is high, increase protocol infusion”, or “If the ICP is low, stop protocol infusion”. These rules are based on collective experience of specialists in the field as well as available literature. Thus, as more fuzzy rules and sets are obtained from various sources, uncertainties are potentially reduced.

Fuzzy Inference System

Fuzzy inference system (FIS) is a framework which is based on fuzzy sets, fuzzy rules and fuzzy reasoning. It has four main components including fuzzifier, rule base, inference engine and Defuzzifier. The fuzzifier creates fuzzy sets from “crisp” values like a fuzzy set for ICP will be divided into “low, normal and high” and a fuzzy set for protocol infusion will be divided into “stop, decrease and increase”. Next, the fuzzy rules are formed based on these two input fuzzy sets: “If the ICP is low, stop protocol infusion”, “If the ICP is normal decrease protocol infusion” and “If the ICP is high, increase protocol infusion”. The inference engine applies all the fuzzy rules on the fuzzy sets to determine the resultant fuzzy output. If a “crisp” output value is required, the process of defuzzification converts the fuzzy output into a “crisp” output value by determining the center of mass of the combined, overlapping membership functions.

The above discussion clearly highlights fuzzy logic as a sensitive and specific tool for various clinical problems. If focused research is conducted, it is possible that in future fuzzy logic play an important role in medical science too.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fuzzy logic offers a powerful thinking way that can deal with uncertainty and imprecision. Uncertainty interval not only provides confident description of the detection results, but also offers double control limits for the detection process, thereby leading to less false negative or false positive and more effective strategy for detecting COVID-19 patients. Combination of knowledge, observation and experience from medical experts is the backbone of a fuzzy models based medical diagnostic system. Literature reveals that fuzzy logic has been used effectively in medical Science. Different types of methodologies have been applied to diagnose the diseases based on symptoms, historical and clinical data of an individual. Increase in the number of recent applications of medicine with fuzzy-logic is an indication of growing popularity of fuzzy systems. Fuzzy intelligent systems developed during 2007–2018 have been studied to explore various techniques applied for disease prediction. Here we are interested to review the important works done on the analysis of fuzzy based mathematical models.

T. Kar and S. Jana (2013) studied the dynamical behavior of the system with fixed control for both vaccination and treatment. Basic reproduction number is obtained in all possible cases and they took controls as time dependent and obtain the optimal control strategy to minimize both the infected populations and the associated costs. Furthermore, fuzzy modeling has a unique advantage the close relationship between the linguistic description and the mathematical model can be used to verify the validity of the verbal explanation suggested by the observer.

R. W. Hndoosh, M. S. Saroa and S. Kumar (2014) analyzed an Adaptive-Network-based Fuzzy Inference System ANFIS with different techniques of clustering is successfully developed to solve one of the problems of medical diagnoses, because it has the advantage of powerful modeling ability. In this paper, they proposed the generation of an adaptive neuro-Fuzzy Inference System model using different clustering models such as a subtractive fuzzy clustering (SFC) model and a fuzzy mean clustering (FCM) model in the Takagi-Sugano (TS) fuzzy model for selecting the hidden node centers.

L. Zadeh (2015) discussed the principal contributions to the development of fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic. Among the contributions which are discussed are: introduction of the concept of a fuzzy set, FL-generalization, the concept of a linguistic variable, information granulation, precipitation of meaning, generalized theory of uncertainty (GTU), the concept of a restriction, restriction-centered theory of truth and meaning, the information principle, and similarity-based definitions of possibility and probability.

P. Cihan (2020) discussed the Covid-19 outbreak appeared in Wuhan in December 2019 and spread rapidly all over the world. In this study, fuzzy rule basing system (FRBS) used to predict the number of Covid-19 daily cases.

S. Chatterjee, A. Sarkar, S. Chatterjee, M. Karmakar and R. Paul (2020) investigated a standard epidemiological model, known as the SIRD model, to study the COVID-19 infection in India, and a few other countries around the world. The projection of the model is highly sensitive to the choice of the parameters and the available data. Besides, since the pandemic is an ongoing dynamic phenomenon, the reported results are subjected to regular updates in consonance with the acquired real data.

C. Yang and J. Wang (2020) proposed a mathematical model to investigate the current outbreak of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Wuhan, China. Their model describes the multiple transmission pathways in the infection dynamics, and emphasizes the role of the environmental reservoir in the transmission and spread of this disease. They conducted a detailed analysis of this model, and demonstrate its application using publicly reported data. Among other findings, they analytical and numerical results indicate that the coronavirus infection would remain endemic, which necessitates long-term disease prevention and intervention programs.

B. Ivorra, M. R. Ferrandez, M. V. Perez and A. M. Ramos (2020) developed a mathematical model for the spread of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). It is a new θ -SEIHRD model (not a SIR, SEIR or other general purpose model), which takes into account the known special characteristics of this disease, as the existence of infectious undetected cases and the different sanitary and infectiousness conditions of hospitalized people. It is complex enough to capture the most important effects, but also simple enough to allow an affordable identification of its parameters, using the data that authorities report on this pandemic.

K. Liang (2020) discussed the purpose of this paper was to reveal the spread rules of the three Pneumonia, COVID-19, SARS and MERS. He compares the new spread characteristics of COVID-19 with those of SARS and MERS. By considering the growth rate and inhibition constant of infectious diseases, their propagation growth model is established. The infection inhibition constant in Hubei is two orders of magnitude lower than in other regions, which reasonably explains the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak in Hubei.

D. Painuli, D. Mishra, S. Bhardwaj and M. Aggarwal (2020) proposed a fuzzy rule-based system which is used with MATLAB tools for simulations to give predictions related to whether one is suffering from Covid19 or not. At present, the testing kits of Covid19 are very limited and they take lot of time to give results but our proposed system can be used in initial predictions, which can save both time and money.

P. Harjule, V. Tiwari and A. Kumar (2021) discussed that World Health Organization (WHO) announced novel coronavirus (COVID-19) disease, a pandemic on March 12, 2020, a disease caused by SARS-CoV2 virus. The main purpose behind this review paper is to convey to the readers the different dimensions of already existing applications and present an initial description of how mathematical modeling can help predict the spread of COVID-19 more accurately and reliably. Finally, a conclusion is drawn regarding the current state-of-the-art methods and their challenges.

Conclusion

We believe that this approach can be utilized in many fields of science, including biology, economics, psychology, sociology and more. In such fields, many linguistic models exist in the research literature, and they can be directly transformed into mathematical models. The Covid-19 outbreak has affected more than 210 countries as of today. The rapid increase in the number of cases caused healthcare industries to collapse. Countries have faced major problems such as medicine, personnel, and hospital capacity. Each country was taken on measures to reduce the spread of the virus.

Although the world has witnessed and survived many pandemics and epidemic in the past, the challenges posed by COVID-19 are unparalleled and unprecedented. The major cause of worry being its rate of spread rather than its mortality. Research resorts to statistical or mathematical models to estimate the spread of an epidemic and to suggest containment measures. These models provide a solid base to validate and analyze the impact of various interventions practiced across the world. Corona viruses are one of the dangerous sources of human infection. It is also necessary to carry out appropriate data analysis, which helps to find solutions to various issues. To do this, use data analysis and forecasting models. Thus, this work is devoted to the review of mathematical models for the analysis and prediction of the distribution of COVID-19.

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